

Electronic structure, reactivity, and predicted biological activity of halogenated isatin-pyridine Schiff bases: a DFT study*

Nikolay Toshev¹

1 Department of Bioorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Plovdiv, 15A Vasil Aprilov Blvd., 4002 Plovdiv, Bulgaria

2 Faculty of Medicine, Medical University of Plovdiv, 15A Vasil Aprilov Blvd, 4002 Plovdiv, Bulgaria

3 Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University Varna, 84 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 9000 Varna, Bulgaria

4 Research Institute at Medical University of Plovdiv, 15A Vasil Aprilov Blvd., 4002 Plovdiv, Bulgaria

5 Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, Plovdiv University "Paisii Hilendarski", 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Nikolay Toshev (nikolay.toshev@mu-plovdiv.bg)

Received 10 February 2026 ♦ Accepted 27 March 2026 ♦ Published 20 April 2026

Citation: Toshev N, Abdollahi A, Mihalev K, Iliev I, Uzunova Y, Delchev V, Agova N, Georgieva S (2026) Electronic structure, reactivity, and predicted biological activity of halogenated isatin-pyridine Schiff bases: a DFT study. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e188309>

Abstract

Isatin derivatives have been at the forefront of pharmaceutical research, displaying a wide range of biological activities, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anticancer properties. In this study, twelve isatin-pyridine Schiff bases were evaluated using density functional theory (DFT) methods to examine the influence of pyridyl ring orientation (2-, 3-, and 4-aminopyridine) and C6-halogen substitution (F, Cl, Br) on electronic structure and reactivity. Frontier molecular orbitals and global reactivity descriptors were calculated to evaluate donor-acceptor properties, charge-transfer ability, and electronic stability. The 2-aminopyridine derivatives display the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) energies, lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) energies, and smallest energy gaps. Chlorine- and bromine-substituted derivatives show enhanced electrophilicity, electronegativity, and ΔN_{\max} , while fluorine has minimal influence. DFT analysis reveals that 6-chloro-3-(2-pyridylimine)-indole-2-one and 6-bromo-3-(2-pyridylimine)-indole-2-one are the most promising candidates, as their electronic features are consistent with enhanced biological activity. These findings provide a basis for the rational design of next-generation isatin-Schiff bases with optimized reactivity and improved biological potential.

Keywords

Biological activity, DFT calculations, frontier orbitals, isatin, reactivity descriptors

* This article is part of: "New horizons in technology transfer in pharmacy", edited by Svetlana Fotkova Georgieva, Georgi Momekov, Alexander Zlatkov, Yoana Kiselova-Kaneva, Rumiana Simeonova, Tsvetelina Velikova, Lyubomir Marinov, Rositsa Mihaylova.

Introduction

Heterocyclic scaffolds play a central role in modern medicinal chemistry due to their structural diversity, drug-like properties, and the potential to interact with different biological targets. The structural versatility and multifaceted nature of isatin and its derivatives have placed these compounds at the forefront of pharmaceutical research, driving extensive efforts toward the design and synthesis of new biologically active compounds. Isatin (1H-indole-2,3-dione) is a privileged heterocyclic scaffold that has inspired a very broad family of derivatives with diverse structural chemistry and multiple applications in medicinal, coordination, and materials chemistry. Its bicyclic framework, consisting of a conjugated benzene ring fused to a five-membered 2,3-dioxindoline ring with an endocyclic nitrogen at position 1, provides multiple sites for chemical modification, thus varying in both electrophilic and nucleophilic reactivity (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Chemical structure of isatin.

This combination of structural rigidity and functional versatility forms the basis for designing libraries of isatin-based small molecules with different physicochemical and biological properties. This structural flexibility creates a basis for understanding the broad spectrum of biological activities associated with isatin derivatives, which are summarized here.

The isatin scaffold has been extensively studied for drug design due to its wide range of biological activities. Isatin

derivatives demonstrate a broad spectrum of biological activities, including anticancer, antioxidant, antibacterial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and anti-HIV activity (Bal et al. 2005; Abbas et al. 2013; Sharma et al. 2016; Heffeter et al. 2019; Guo 2019; Yakan et al. 2021). This variety of reported activities highlights the isatin scaffold's flexibility and its ability to engage multiple biological targets. The isatin scaffold also serves as a building block for isatin hybrid structures such as Schiff bases, hydrazones, thiosemicarbazones, and others (Medvedev et al. 2007; Enamullah et al. 2020; Al-Rasheed et al. 2023). These structural modifications alter the electronic distribution, hydrogen-bonding patterns, and three-dimensional shapes of the molecules, leading to changes in frontier molecular orbital energies and global reactivity descriptors. To understand how these biological activities occur, it is essential to analyze the key functionalization strategies that influence the structure and reactivity of isatin derivatives.

The indolin-2-one core of isatin provides several sites for chemical modification (Fig. 2).

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the isatin scaffold has several chemically accessible positions, including N-1, C-3, and the aromatic C-5 to C-7, which allow for systematic functional group introduction. The C-3 carbonyl and adjacent nitrogen can form imines (Schiff bases), which serve as linkers to connect aromatic and heterocyclic fragments. The Schiff-base linkage is a favored method, as many such compounds display bioactivity (Meshram et al. 2025). Halogenation of the aromatic ring is another established strategy. Electrophilic substitution allows the introduction of fluoro, chloro, bromo, and iodo groups at the C-5, C-6, and C-7 positions. Substitution at the aromatic C-5 position with halogens (F, Cl, Br), methyl, or methoxy groups has been systematically explored in several studies (Çavuş et al. 2020). Such substituent variation modulates the electron density across the isatin scaffold, affecting antioxidant activity and computed parameters such as the HOMO–

Figure 2. Principal functionalization pathways of the isatin scaffold.

LUMO gap. Halogens significantly influence chemical activity by affecting electronegativity and polarizability, resulting in changes in electronic distribution and molecular recognition. Additionally, functionalization at the C-3 position into an imine or hydrazone moiety creates isatin-Schiff bases, carbohydrazones, and thiosemicarbazones. These modifications introduce additional donor atoms (N, O, S), conjugated linkers, and intramolecular hydrogen bonds, which are essential for biological activity. Consequently, C-6 halogen derivatives, compounds of key interest in this study, can alter lipophilicity and facilitate halogen binding within molecular targets. These transformations also enable the construction of hybrid frameworks in which isatin is combined with different pharmacophoric elements, as described in the next section.

Through the employment of different molecular hybridization techniques, the isatin scaffold can be linked with other pharmacophores, thus creating new hybrids (Patil et al. 2024). Such examples include isatin-thiazole hybrids, isatin-chalcones, and bis-isatin derivatives (Mary et al. 2021). As a result, these hybrid molecules have improved biological performance, increased membrane permeability, and display more favorable electronic properties. Isatin-derived drugs such as Sunitinib illustrate how an isatin-based scaffold can be incorporated into hybrid molecules with improved target affinity and selectivity (Karati et al. 2024). Asymmetric bis-isatin derivatives containing urea or thiourea linkers are connected to two isatin units through a flexible and semi-rigid chain and contain multiple carbonyl and heteroatom donors and extended conjugation. Similarly, unsymmetric bishydrazones formed from isatin hydrazones and substituted salicylaldehyde further explore this concept by combining phenolic and isatin-derived donor sets in ligands (Kaya et al. 2021). Moreover, the structural diversity of isatin also includes spirocyclic and fused ring systems (Singh et al. 2012). Spiro derivatives exhibit different conformational behavior and have been evaluated as anticancer agents (Parakkal et al. 2023). Additional studies have expanded the isatin framework into hybrid pharmacophores, combining the isatin scaffold with triazine, thiadiazole, triazole, and chalcone (Ghosh et al. 2021). For example, isatin-s-triazine hydrazones and isatin chalcones incorporating a triazine moiety have been studied for antioxidant and kinase-related activities, supported by detailed study of their electronic descriptors and docking behavior (Al-Rasheed et al. 2023). Likewise, variation of the aryl substituent on the thiadiazole rings, linked to isatin through an acyl spacer at C-3, has generated a series of analogues with different lipophilicity and polar surface area, several of which have been considered as potential anticancer candidates (Rasgania et al. 2023). The presence of donor atoms in the isatin scaffold introduced through hydrazone, imine, or thiosemicarbazone groups makes isatin derivatives multidentate ligands in metal complexes.

Metal coordination can modify the parent ligand's geometry, redox properties, and lipophilicity, improving cellular uptake or proposing novel binding modes in enzymes, resulting in metal complexes with enhanced bioactivity.

Isatin hydrazones, bishydrazones, and Schiff bases act as multidentate chelators, forming stable metal complexes with transition metal ions such as Mn(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), Cr(III), Co(II), and Zn(II) (Adam et al. 2023; Nalini et al. 2023). These metal chelates exhibit enhanced antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anticancer activities compared to the isatin derivatives, highlighting the important role of metal coordination in modulating chemical structure and biological activity. Taken together, these findings reinforce the idea that the isatin moiety is an appropriate scaffold for linking different organic frameworks to divalent ions, producing drug candidates with improved pharmacological potential.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study providing a comparative DFT analysis of both halogen substitution and pyridine ring orientation within the isatin-Schiff base scaffold with respect to the electronic structure and global reactivity descriptors.

Due to the variety of isatin derivatives, computational approaches play a valuable role in understanding their physicochemical and biological properties. Nowadays, density functional theory (DFT) has emerged as an important tool for investigating the electronic structure of these compounds. DFT calculations, often using functionals such as B3LYP with different combinations of basis sets, can optimize the geometries of isatin derivatives and evaluate key reactivity descriptors (Bakir et al. 2018; Muğlu et al. 2019; Raksha et al. 2025). The energies of the frontier molecular orbitals (HOMO and LUMO) are results of DFT calculations, together with global reactivity descriptors derived from them, and are central outcomes of such analysis.

Materials and methods

Studied molecules

In this study, a series of 6-halogenated derivatives of 3-(pyridylimine)-1H-indole-2-one were designed to explore how pyridyl ring orientation and halogen substitution influence electronic structure and reactivity. Three structural series were examined, each incorporating a Schiff base linkage between isatin and a pyridinylamine isomer (2-, 3-, or 4-aminopyridine), yielding 3-(2-pyridylimine), 3-(3-pyridylimine), and 3-(4-pyridylimine) derivatives. Within each series, halogen atoms (fluorine, chlorine, or bromine) were introduced at the 6-position of the isatin scaffold to evaluate their electronic and steric effects on molecular reactivity and potential biological activity. These molecules share a common scaffold, allowing a systematic comparison of the electronic and steric effects arising from pyridyl ring orientation and halogen variation. The structures of the molecules are shown in Fig. 3.

Computational methodology

All calculations were performed with the Gaussian 16 suite of programs (Frisch et al. 2016). Previous studies have shown that the B3LYP functional and the 6-311++G(d, p)

Series	No.	Compound	R1	R2
A	1	2-AP	-H	
	2	6-F-2-AP	-F	
	3	6-Cl-2-AP	-Cl	
	4	6-Br-2-AP	-Br	
B	5	3-AP	-H	
	6	6-F-3-AP	-F	
	7	6-Cl-3-AP	-Cl	
	8	6-Br-3-AP	-Br	
C	9	4-AP	-H	
	10	6-F-4-AP	-F	
	11	6-Cl-4-AP	-Cl	
	12	6-Br-4-AP	-Br	

R2 substituents are shown as free amines; the final compounds contain the corresponding imine (=N-) linkage formed upon condensation with isatin.

Figure 3. Chemical structures of the designed isatin Schiff base derivatives grouped by aminopyridine position and halogen substitution.

basis set accurately represent the geometries and properties of the studied molecules (Krishnan et al. 1980; Lee et al. 1988; Becke et al. 1993; Becke et al. 1996). It should be noted that the inclusion of polarization functions (d, p) in the calculations enhances the flexibility of the electron density distribution, especially in systems containing multiple heteroatoms and conjugated π -systems. This results in improved accuracy of molecular geometries and electronic properties. Additionally, in this study, diffuse functions (++) were incorporated to better describe electron density in regions distant from the nuclei. Initially, the structures of the studied molecules were optimized in the gas phase. All structures were optimized to a local potential energy minimum, and no imaginary frequencies were found. To account for solvent effects, the Polarizable Continuum Model (PCM) was employed. In this method, the studied molecule is placed in a cavity that is part of a continuous polarizable dielectric medium representing the solvent. In this study, calculations were performed in water with a dielectric constant of $\epsilon = 78$. The structures were generated using ChemCraft software (Chemcraft, Version 1.8 (build 682), 2010, available at: <http://www.chemcraftprog.com>, 2010).

Results and discussion

Frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) and global reactivity descriptors

The molecular orbitals, HOMO and LUMO, were computed employing quantum chemistry techniques. For all studied molecules, DFT calculations were performed at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d, p) level of theory. The optimized geometries of all twelve isatin Schiff base derivatives, grouped into the three pyridyl series, are shown in Fig. 4. Analysis of the HOMO and LUMO orbitals provides valuable insight into their electronic structure and reactivity. In this study, the frontier molecular orbital energies and

global reactivity descriptors were calculated for three isatin Schiff base isomers—2-AP, 3-AP, and 4-AP—together with their corresponding 6-halogenated derivatives (F, Cl, Br substituted at the C6 position of the indole ring). The discussion focuses on how these descriptors rank the molecules relative to one another, both across the three parent isomers and within each halogen series. The computed and calculated values are summarized in Tables 1–3.

HOMO and LUMO analysis

The energy gap between HOMO and LUMO is an essential variable in assessing molecular properties. Moreover, data obtained from HOMO energies reveal the molecule's ability to serve as an electron donor, while LUMO emphasizes its potential as an electron acceptor. The HOMO–LUMO energy gap (ΔE) measures molecular stability and chemical reactivity. Softer, more polarizable, and more reactive molecules typically have smaller energy gaps, whereas harder species are more inert (Fukui et al. 1982). They interact more effectively with radical species or electron-rich sites in biomolecules, contributing to antioxidant activity (Bakir et al. 2024). Moreover, a reduced energy band gap improves biological and pharmacological activity in the context of drug molecules or candidates by making charge-transfer processes and binding to biological targets easier (Misra et al. 2015).

The HOMO energies in the series extend from -6.46 eV (highest, in the 2-AP derivative) to -6.82 eV (lowest, in the 4-AP derivative), reflecting the influence of structural variation among the isomers. Among the three positional isomers (2-AP, 3-AP, 4-AP), the 2-AP derivative shows the highest HOMO (-6.46 eV) energy, consistent with a more electron-rich, nucleophilic character. In contrast, the 3-AP and 4-AP derivatives possess more stabilized HOMO energies (≈ -6.70 eV). This ordering arises from differences in conjugation between the pyridylimine and the isatin core. The ortho position of the nitrogen in the 2-AP derivative allows additional resonance stabilization between

Figure 4. B3LYP/6-311++G(d, p) optimized structures in water of A. 2-AP series; B. 3-AP series; C. 4-AP series.

the pyridylimine and isatin scaffold compared to 3-AP and 4-AP, where the HOMO energy is decreased. Within the halogen series, the introduction of a halogen at C6 lowers the HOMO energy. For example, in the 2-AP derivative, the HOMO is lowered from -6.46 eV to -6.66 eV upon bromine substitution, representing the largest shift. The same pattern is observed in the 4-AP series, where the parent value -6.69 eV shifts downward to -6.81 eV for the 6-bromo derivative. In contrast, the 3-AP derivatives exhibit minimal changes (< 0.02 eV), suggesting that the

3-AP scaffold is less affected by the inductive effect of the halogen at C6. Overall, the highest HOMO is observed in the 2-AP derivative, while the lowest value occurs in the 6-fluoro and 6-Cl-4-AP derivatives (-6.82 eV). These results suggest that 2-AP derivatives are the most prone to oxidation, while the halogenated 4-AP derivatives are more inert and resistant to oxidation. This aligns with previous studies of isatin Schiff bases, which showed that higher HOMO energies and narrower HOMO–LUMO gaps correlate with improved radical-scavenging properties (Bakır

Table 1. Computed energies (in eV) of the HOMO and LUMO, energy gap ΔE , ionization potential (IP), electron affinity (EA), electronegativity (χ), chemical hardness (η), chemical potential (μ), softness (ζ), electrophilicity index (ω), and maximum charge transfer index (ΔN_{\max}), using the B3LYP/6-311++G(d, p) basis set for the 2-AP Schiff base series and their halogenated derivatives.

	E_{HOMO}	E_{LUMO}	ΔE	IP	EA	χ	η	μ	ζ	ω	ΔN_{\max}
2-AP	-6.46	-3.05	3.41	6.46	3.05	4.76	1.70	-4.76	0.59	6.64	2.79
6-F-2-AP	-6.55	-3.08	3.48	6.55	3.08	4.81	1.74	-4.81	0.58	6.67	2.77
6-Cl-2-AP	-6.56	-3.13	3.43	6.56	3.13	4.84	1.71	-4.84	0.58	6.85	2.83
6-Br-2-AP	-6.66	-3.05	3.62	6.66	3.05	4.86	1.81	-4.86	0.55	6.52	2.69

Table 2. Computed energies (in eV) of the HOMO and LUMO, energy gap ΔE , ionization potential (IP), electron affinity (EA), electronegativity (χ), chemical hardness (η), chemical potential (μ), softness (ζ), electrophilicity index (ω), and maximum charge transfer index (ΔN_{\max}), using the B3LYP/6-311++G(d, p) basis set for the 3-AP Schiff base series and their halogenated derivatives.

	E_{HOMO}	E_{LUMO}	ΔE	IP	EA	χ	η	μ	ζ	ω	ΔN_{\max}
3-AP	-6.71	-2.94	3.77	6.71	2.94	4.82	1.89	-4.82	0.53	6.16	2.56
6-F-3-AP	-6.71	-2.94	3.77	6.71	2.94	4.82	1.89	-4.82	0.53	6.16	2.56
6-Cl-3-AP	-6.72	-3.00	3.71	6.72	3.00	4.86	1.86	-4.86	0.54	6.36	2.62
6-Br-3-AP	-6.70	-3.02	3.68	6.70	3.02	4.86	1.84	-4.86	0.54	6.41	2.64

Table 3. Computed energies (in eV) of the HOMO and LUMO, energy gap ΔE , ionization potential (IP), electron affinity (EA), electronegativity (χ), chemical hardness (η), chemical potential (μ), softness (ζ), electrophilicity index (ω), and maximum charge transfer index (ΔN_{\max}), using the B3LYP/6-311++G(d, p) basis set for the 4-AP Schiff base series and their halogenated derivatives.

	E_{HOMO}	E_{LUMO}	ΔE	IP	EA	χ	η	μ	ζ	ω	ΔN_{\max}
4-AP	-6.69	-2.90	3.79	6.69	2.90	4.80	1.89	-4.80	0.53	6.07	2.53
6-F-4-AP	-6.82	-2.93	3.90	6.82	2.93	4.88	1.95	-4.88	0.51	6.10	2.50
6-Cl-4-AP	-6.82	-3.00	3.83	6.82	3.00	4.91	1.91	-4.91	0.52	6.30	2.57
6-Br-4-AP	-6.81	-3.01	3.80	6.81	3.01	4.91	1.90	-4.91	0.53	6.34	2.58

et al. 2024). From a reactivity standpoint, compounds with lower LUMO energies have greater electrophilic character. More negative LUMO values show stronger electron-accepting ability and greater electrophilicity. In the series, the calculated LUMO energies are in the interval -3.13 eV (6-Cl-2-AP) to -2.90 eV (4-AP). Among the three parent scaffolds (2-AP, 3-AP, and 4-AP), the 2-AP derivative has the lowest LUMO, followed by 3-AP (-2.94 eV) and 4-AP (-2.90 eV). The enhanced electron-accepting ability of the 2-AP parent molecule can be attributed to the ortho orientation of the pyridine nitrogen, which leads to additional π -conjugation between the pyridyl ring, imine linkage, and the isatin carbonyl group. In contrast, the para position in 4-AP parent molecules results in reduced delocalization and a higher LUMO. Halogen substitution at the C6 position produces only modest shifts (< 0.10 eV) in LUMO energies, with Cl and Br slightly lowering LUMO and F having minimal influence. One possible explanation is that fluorine, having strong negative inductive effects, has a weaker influence than orbital overlap in the p - π system.

HOMO–LUMO energy gap (ΔE)

In this series, ΔE values range from 3.41 eV for the 2-AP to 3.90 eV for the 6-F-4-AP. The 2-AP derivative displays the narrowest gap (3.41 eV), showing higher reactivity than the corresponding 3-AP (3.77 eV) and 4-AP (3.79 eV). The introduction of a halogen at the C6 position leads to a modest increase in ΔE (≈ 0.10 eV), resulting in slight stabilization of frontier orbital energies. For example, in

the 2-AP series, the energy gap rises from 3.41 eV (parent molecule) to 3.62 eV for the 6-Br-2-AP. Overall, the 2-AP series, displaying the smallest energy gap, is expected to be the most reactive and electronically soft, while 6-F-4-AP, with the widest gap, represents the least reactive derivative in the series. These observations align with previous studies on isatin Schiff bases, where narrower energy gaps have been correlated with enhanced radical-scavenging behavior in antioxidant assays (Bakır et al. 2024).

Ionization potential (IP)

The energy needed to remove an electron from the molecules is known as ionization potential, which corresponds to HOMO ionization. According to the Koopmans theorem, $IP = -E(\text{HOMO})$, such that compounds with lower IP values donate electrons more easily (Koopmans 1934). Given this, across the entire set of derivatives, IP values range from 6.46 eV for 2-AP to 6.82 eV for both the 6-F-4-AP and 6-Cl-4-AP. Thus, 2-AP is the most easily ionized derivative, while the halogenated 4-AP derivatives show the greatest resistance to electron removal. Halogen substitution stabilizes the HOMO levels, leading to increased IP values. The largest halogen-induced shift is observed in the 2-AP series, where IP increases from 6.46 eV (parent molecule) to 6.66 eV for the 6-Br-2-AP. Fluorine and chlorine induce smaller changes in the series compared to bromine derivatives. Adjustment of IP serves as a useful approach for fine-tuning molecular behavior. Molecules with low IP are prone to oxidation and show poor chemical stability, whereas those

with high IP may not be reactive enough to participate in physiologically relevant processes. The IP values obtained here (6.46 eV–6.82 eV) indicate that all twelve derivatives remain capable of oxidation under biological conditions.

Electron affinity (EA)

Electron affinity (EA) indicates the tendency of a molecule to undergo reduction. According to the Koopmans theorem, $EA = -E(\text{LUMO})$, so that higher EA values correspond to more negative LUMO levels and a stronger drive to accept an electron. In the series, values range from 2.90 eV for 4-AP to 3.13 eV for 6-Cl-2-AP, as shown in Tables 1–3. Due to LUMO stabilization, halogen derivatives have a modest increase in EA, especially in the 4-AP series. For example, the 6-Br-4-AP derivative exhibits an EA increase of approximately 0.11 eV relative to the parent molecule. A similar but slightly smaller increase is observed in the 3-AP series, where the 6-Br-3-AP shows an EA increase of ≈ 0.08 eV. The 2-AP derivatives show varied behavior: 2-AP and 6-Br-2-AP values are similar (3.05 eV), but 6-Cl-2AP increases to 3.13 eV. Such an effect in the chlorine analogues is a result of inductive effects and polarization. Fluorine, in contrast, produces minimal effect, with 6-F-2-AP showing a slight increase (3.08 eV), while fluorination of 3-AP has no effect. EA contributes directly to the electrophilicity index and influences how these molecules may interact with nucleophilic enzyme residues in proteins. Highly electrophilic structures can show increased reactivity toward nucleophilic sites. Based on EA values, we can suggest that 2-AP derivatives, particularly 6-Cl-2-AP, possess the strongest electron-accepting character.

Global hardness (η) and softness (ζ)

Global hardness (η) and softness (ζ) indicate how resistant a molecule is to the redistribution of its electron density. Hardness is equal to: $\eta = \frac{1}{2} (E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO}))$, while softness ($\zeta = 1/\eta$). Hard molecules resist charge deformation and exhibit higher energy gaps, whereas soft molecules are more easily polarized and often participate in charge-transfer processes (Parr et al. 1983). Softer molecules (lower η , higher ζ) generally display greater chemical reactivity and interact more effectively with biological targets because their electron density can be more readily reorganized (Parr et al. 1983). This electronic flexibility may facilitate radical scavenging, electron transfer, and the formation of non-covalent interactions within enzyme binding sites.

The hardness values in this series fall within a relatively narrow window (1.70–1.95 eV), with softness values between 0.51 and 0.59 eV⁻¹. The softest compound is the parent 2-AP ($\eta = 1.70$ eV, $\zeta = 0.59$ eV⁻¹), whereas 6-F-4-AP is the hardest ($\eta = 1.95$ eV, $\zeta = 0.51$ eV⁻¹). Among the three scaffolds, 2-AP is softer than both 3-AP and 4-AP, which both exhibit similar hardness values ($\eta = 1.89$ eV). Halogenated derivatives generally show slightly increased hardness, except for a mild softening observed in the 3-AP series. Overall, the greater softness of 2-AP derivatives suggests enhanced reactivity and improved antioxidant behavior. In contrast, the 4-AP scaffold is more rigid and chemically stable. From a chem-

ical standpoint, these different structures provide a balance between the higher reactivity of 2-AP and the greater stability of 4-AP, depending on the biological application.

Chemical potential (μ) and electronegativity (χ)

Chemical potential (μ) is defined as $\mu = -\chi$. Electronegativity integrates information from both ionization potential (IP) and electron affinity (EA), providing a measure of how strongly a molecule attracts or retains electron density. More electronegative compounds stabilize additional electronic density and display stronger electrophilic behavior in chemical reactions. Modulation of chemical potential and electronegativity through positional isomerism or substituent variation in the isatin scaffold provides a rational approach for adjustment of electronic character and, consequently, biological capability.

Regarding these descriptors, as shown in Tables 1–3, the χ values across the series range from 4.76 to 4.91 eV, with corresponding chemical potential (μ) values between -4.76 and -4.91 eV. The 2-AP is the least electronegative ($\chi = 4.76$ eV), whereas the 6-Cl-4-AP and 6-Br-4-AP display the highest electronegativity ($\chi = 4.91$ eV). Electronegativity increases slightly from 2-AP to 4-AP, suggesting similar electron-withdrawing properties throughout the three scaffolds. The introduction of a halogen at C6 increases electronegativity across all series. For example, in the 4-AP derivatives, electronegativity increases from 4.80 eV in the parent compound to 4.91 eV in both 6-Br-4-AP and 6-Cl-4-AP. Within the current dataset, halogenated 4-AP derivatives display the highest electronegativity and lowest chemical potential. In contrast, 2-AP possesses the lowest electronegativity (χ) and the highest chemical potential (μ), showing a greater tendency for electron donation and participation in nucleophilic reactions. Thus, the 6-Cl-4-AP and 6-Br-4-AP are more suitable for electrophilic reactions, whereas 2-AP derivatives are expected to be more effective in electron-transfer or redox reactions. From a biological perspective, highly electronegative molecules can interact with electron-rich protein residues, thus influencing binding affinity and reactivity. Previous studies have shown that increased electronegativity in Schiff bases can be used as a predictor for antibacterial activity and may contribute to enhanced interactions with microbial targets (Hubenova et al. 2018). In the series, the increased electronegativity of 4-AP derivatives occurs together with increased hydrophobicity, and as a result, this may lead to improved membrane permeability and electron-attracting capacity.

Electrophilicity index (ω)

The electrophilicity index (ω) was introduced as a qualitative measure of a molecule's tendency to accept electron density (Parr et al. 1983; Domingo et al. 2002). The formula that was used for these calculations is $\omega = \mu^2/2\eta$. This descriptor incorporates both the driving force for electron uptake, represented by chemical potential (μ), and the resistance to charge deformation, expressed

through hardness (η). Taken together, these provide an effective measure of the overall electrophilic strength.

In this series, ω values range from 6.07 eV for 4-AP to 6.85 eV for the 6-Cl-2-AP. Although 6-Cl-4-AP displays the highest electronegativity, its electrophilicity values increase only modestly, reaching 6.30–6.34 eV. The 3-AP analogues show intermediate electrophilicity (6.36–6.41 eV). The sole exception is the set of fluoro-substituted derivatives of all initial scaffolds, where halogen derivatives produce only a very slight increase in ω compared to the parent scaffolds (≈ 0.03 eV), indicating the least impact of fluorine on electrophilicity among the studied halogens.

High electrophilicity may contribute positively to biological activity by enhancing interactions with nucleophilic residues and additionally promoting non-specific covalent interactions and toxicity. Although the ω values observed here (6.07–6.85 eV) are moderate, the relative differences within the series remain significant. Based on these values, the 6-Cl-2-AP is the most electrophilic molecule due to the combination of low hardness ($\eta = 1.71$ eV) and moderate chemical potential ($\mu = -4.84$ eV). In contrast, the 4-AP, showing the lowest ω , is expected to behave as a weaker electrophile and has more inert behavior toward nucleophilic species. In all scaffolds, the introduction of a halogen at the C6 position increases ω , potentially affecting interactions with nucleophilic residues in biomolecules.

Maximum charge transfer index (ΔN_{\max})

The maximum number of electrons that an electrophile or nucleophile can accept is defined as (ΔN_{\max}) (Parr et al. 1999). Across the series, all Schiff bases display ΔN_{\max} values between 2.5 and 2.83, implying that molecules in the study can accept two to three electrons. The highest value (2.83) was observed for 6-Cl-2-AP, while the lowest (2.50) was for 6-F-2-AP. This trend coincides with the calculated softness and electrophilicity patterns, since ΔN_{\max} scales with μ/η . This is a result of the large negative value of chemical potential (μ) and low hardness (η), whereas 6-F-2-AP, which has increased hardness, limits its ability to stabilize electron density. The introduction of halogen substituents at the C-6 position of the isatin core influences ΔN_{\max} to varying extents; however, the overall effect remains minimal across the series. The maximum charge transfer index is not a direct regulator of biological activity, but it reflects some aspects of charge distribution that can influence interactions with nucleophilic biomolecules or metal ions. Moreover, the results match electronic trends: 2-AP-based structures are the most flexible and reactive, while 4-AP derivatives are more electronically stable.

Dipole moment

Dipole moment is a key molecular property indicating the polarity of a molecule—how the positive and negative charges are separated. It influences solubility, cell permeability, and binding interactions. Dipole moments in the series range from 5.25 D up to 8.41 D (Table 4).

Table 4. Dipole moments (in Debye) for the studied molecules.

Series	Molecule	Dipole moment (Debye)
A	2-AP	7.37
	6-F-2-AP	5.37
	6-Cl-2-AP	5.32
	6-Br-2-AP	5.39
B	3-AP	7.43
	6-F-3-AP	5.29
	6-Cl-3-AP	5.25
	6-Br-3-AP	5.25
C	4-AP	8.41
	6-F-4-AP	6.25
	6-Cl-4-AP	6.17
	6-Br-4-AP	6.23

The highest polarity is observed for the 4-AP (8.41 D), whereas the lowest corresponds to 6-Cl-3-AP and 6-Br-3-AP (5.25 D). Among the parent isomers, the trend is as follows: 2-AP (7.37 D) < 3-AP (7.43 D) < 4-AP (8.41 D), resulting in increasing polarity as the pyridine nitrogen moves from the ortho position to the para position in the pyridine moiety. One possible explanation is that, in 2-AP, an intramolecular hydrogen bond between the ortho-pyridine nitrogen and the isatin reduces the net dipole moment, while in 4-AP, the groups are more spatially separated, thus yielding a higher dipole moment. Halogen derivatives have lower dipole moments compared to the parent molecules. For instance, 2-AP (7.37 D) decreases to 5.32 D in 6-Cl-2-AP and 5.39 D in 6-Br-2-AP. A similar reduction is observed in the 3-AP series, where all halogenated derivatives fall to approximately 5.25 D. The 4-AP scaffold also shows a decrease, with dipole moments ranging from 8.41 D to approximately 6.20 D upon halogen substitution at the C6 position.

Overall, the calculated descriptors reveal structure–reactivity relationships across the studied isatin-pyridine Schiff bases. The 2-AP derivatives have higher HOMO energies, smaller HOMO–LUMO gaps, and lower hardness values. They are more reactive and donate electrons more easily. Halogen substitution at C6 modulates these properties, with Cl and Br making them more electrophilic than F, particularly by increasing electrophilicity. Additionally, pyridyl ring orientation significantly influences polarity, and the introduction of halogens reduces the dipole moment. The results obtained show that the type of substituent and the position of the pyridyl ring tune the electronic properties of the studied molecules.

Conclusion

This DFT study demonstrates that pyridyl ring orientation and 6-halogen substitution exert strong and predictable effects on the electronic structure and reactivity of isatin-pyridine Schiff bases. Notably, electronic reactivity in isatin-pyridine hybrids can be tuned through a combination of ring orientation and halogen substitution.

Among the three positional isomers, the 2-AP derivatives have the most reactive electronic profiles, characterized by the highest HOMO, the lowest LUMO, and the smallest energy gap, identifying them as the most electronically flexible and prone to charge transfer. In contrast, the 3-AP and 4-AP derivatives have more stabilized orbitals and lower reactivity. Halogen substitution at the C6 position introduces additional modulation of electronic properties. Across all pyridyl orientations, halogens lower the HOMO and stabilize the LUMO levels through an inductive electron-withdrawing effect, with chlorine and bromine having the strongest effect. Fluorine has the smallest effect. Moreover, subtle deviations—such as the softer, less electrophilic 6-Br-2-AP analog—highlight the balance between inductive and resonance effects.

Overall, 6-Cl-2-AP and 6-Br-2-AP derivatives emerge as prospective candidates, combining high reactivity, electrophilicity, and improved lipophilicity. These insights provide a predictive framework for selecting isatin-pyridine Schiff bases with optimal reactivity, electrophilicity, and lipophilicity for antioxidant, antimicrobial, or anticancer applications.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

References

- Abbas SY, Farag AA, Ammar YA, Atreas AA, Mohamed AF, El-Henawy AA (2013) Synthesis, characterization, and antiviral activity of novel fluorinated isatin derivatives. *Monatshefte für Chemie – Chemical Monthly* 144(11): 1725–1733. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00706-013-1034-3>
- Adam MSS, Abdel-Rahman OS, Makhlof MM (2023) Metal ion induced changes in the structure of Schiff base hydrazone chelates and their reactivity effect on catalytic benzyl alcohol oxidation and biological assays. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1272: 134164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2022.134164>
- Al-Rasheed HH, Al-Khamis SA, Barakat A, El-Faham A, Haukka M, Soliman SM (2023) Synthesis and characterizations of novel isatin-s-triazine hydrazone derivatives: X-ray structure, Hirshfeld analysis and DFT calculations. *Crystals* 13: 305. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst13020305>
- Bakır T, Sayiner HS, Kandemirli F (2018) Experimental and theoretical investigation of antioxidant activity and capacity of thiosemicarbazones based on isatin derivatives. *Phosphorus, Sulfur, and Silicon and the Related Elements* 193(8): 493–499. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10426507.2018.1452232>
- Bakır TK, Çavuş MS, Muğlu H, Yakan H (2024) Synthesis, structure elucidation, antioxidant properties, and theoretical calculations of new Schiff bases–isatin derivatives. *Research on Chemical Intermediates* 50: 3937–3962. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11164-024-05318-1>
- Bal TR, Anand B, Yogeewari P, Sriram D (2005) Synthesis and evaluation of anti-HIV activity of isatin beta-thiosemicarbazone derivatives. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters* 15(20): 4451–4455. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2005.07.046>

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

This work was supported by the Science Fund of the Medical University of Varna under Project No. 23009, titled “Design, Synthesis, and Study of Isatin Hybrid Molecules with Presumed Broad-Spectrum Antimicrobial Activity and Potential Application in Implantology,” led by Prof. Svetlana Fotkova Georgieva, and the European Union—NextGeneration EU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, Project No. BG-RRP-2.004-0009-C02.

The research that led to these results was carried out using the infrastructure purchased under the national Roadmap for RI, financially coordinated by the MES of the Republic of Bulgaria (grant № D01-98/26.06.2025).

Author contributions

Conceptualization, N.T. and S.G.; investigation, N.T., A.A., K.M., Y.U., V.D.; writing – original draft preparation, N.T., A.A., K.M., I.I., Y.U.; writing – review and editing, N.T., A.A., K.M., I.I., Y.U., S.G.; visualization, N.T. and N.A.; supervision, N.T., V.D., and S.G.; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Nikolay Toshev <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3637-6897>
 Armina Abdollahi <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-7972-6467>
 Kaloyan Mihalev <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-8650-1220>
 Ivelin Iliev <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9388-9838>
 Yordanka Uzunova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6423-5998>
 Vassil Delchev <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8305-413X>
 Nadya Agova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0342-4672>
 Svetlana Georgieva <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4483-0674>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

- Becke AD (1993) Density-functional thermochemistry. III. The role of exact exchange. *Journal of Chemical Physics* 98: 5648–5652. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.464913>
- Becke AD (1996) Density-functional thermochemistry. IV. A new dynamical correlation functional and implications for exact-exchange mixing. *Journal of Chemical Physics* 104: 1040–1046. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.470829>
- Çavuş MS, Yakan H, Muğlu H, Bakır T (2020) Novel carbohydrazones including 5-substituted isatin: Synthesis, characterization, and quantum-chemical studies on the relationship between electronic and antioxidant properties. *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids* 140: 109362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpics.2020.109362>
- Chemcraft (2010) Graphical software for visualization of quantum chemistry computations. Version 1.8, build 682. <http://www.chemcraftprog.com>
- Domingo LR, Aurell MJ, Pérez P, Contreras R (2002) Quantitative characterization of the global electrophilicity power of common diene/dienophile pairs in Diels–Alder reactions. *Tetrahedron* 58(22): 4417–4423. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4020\(02\)00410-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4020(02)00410-6)
- Enamullah M, Al-Moktadir Zaman M, Bindu MM, Islam MK, Islam MA (2020) Experimental and theoretical studies on isatin-Schiff bases and their copper(II) complexes: Syntheses, spectroscopy, tautomerism, redox potentials, EPR, PXRD and DFT/TDDFT. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1201: 127207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2019.127207>
- Frisch MJ, Trucks GW, Schlegel HB (2016) Gaussian 16, Revision C.01. Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford, CT. <https://gaussian.com>
- Fukui K (1982) Role of frontier orbitals in chemical reactions. *Science* 218(4574): 747–754. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.218.4574.747>
- Ghosh S, Ramarao TA, Samanta PK, Jha A, Satpati P, Sen A (2021) Triazole-based isatin derivatives as potential inhibitors of key cancer-promoting kinases: Insight from electronic structure, docking and molecular dynamics simulations. *Journal of Molecular Graphics and Modelling* 107: 107944. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmgm.2021.107944>
- Guo H (2019) Isatin derivatives and their antibacterial activities. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 164: 678–688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2018.12.017>
- Heffeter P, Pape VFS, Enyedy ÉA, Keppler BK, Szakacs G, Kowol CR (2019) Anticancer thiosemicarbazones: Chemical properties, interaction with iron metabolism, and resistance development. *Antioxidants & Redox Signaling* 30(8): 1062–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2017.7487>
- Hubenova Y, Bakalska R, Mitov M (2018) Electrodeposited styrylquinolinium dye as molecular electrocatalyst for coupled redox reactions. *Bioelectrochemistry* 123: 173–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioelchem.2018.05.006>
- Karati D (2024) An insight into isatin and its hybrid scaffolds as anti-cancer agents: An explicative review. *Discover Chemistry* 1: 73. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44371-024-00073-z>
- Kaya Y, Erçağ A, Serdaroğlu G, Kaya S, Barden I, Rocha B (2021) Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization, DFT calculations, and molecular docking studies of new unsymmetric bishydrazone derivatives. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1244: 131224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2021.131224>
- Koopmans T (1934) Über die Zuordnung von Wellenfunktionen und Eigenwerten zu den einzelnen Elektronen eines Atoms. *Physica* 1(1–6): 104–113. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-8914\(34\)90011-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-8914(34)90011-2)
- Krishnan R, Binkley JS, Seeger R, Pople JA (1980) Self-consistent molecular orbital methods. XX. A basis set for correlated wave functions. *Journal of Chemical Physics* 72: 650–654. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.438955>
- Lee C, Yang W, Parr RG (1988) Development of the Colle–Salvetti correlation-energy formula into a functional of the electron density. *Physical Review B: Condensed Matter* 37(2): 785–789. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.37.785>
- Mary YS, Mary S, Çetindağ A (2021) Biological perspective of a triazine derivative with isatin/chalcone/acridone: DFT and docking investigations. *Structural Chemistry* 32: 1609–1620. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11224-020-01609-6>
- Medvedev A, Buneeva O, Glover V (2007) Biological targets for isatin and its analogues: Implications for therapy. *Biologics* 1(2): 151–162.
- Meshram P, Dongre R, Ahmed M, Ahmed S, Gajendhiran R, Kalilur Rahiman A, Ben Hadda T, Fehelbom KM, Bhat AR, Tataringa G (2025) Design, synthesis and antibacterial activity of new isatin-based Schiff base derivatives: Molecular docking, POM analysis, in silico pharmacokinetics and identification of antitumor pharmacophore sites. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1322(3): 140508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2024.140508>
- Misra SK, Ghoshal G, Gartia MR, Wu Z, De AK, Ye M, Bromfield CR, Williams EM, Singh K, Tangella KV, Rund L, Schulten K, Schook LB, Ray PS, Burdette EC, Pan D (2015) Trimodal therapy: Combining hyperthermia with repurposed bexarotene and ultrasound for treating liver cancer. *ACS Nano* 9(11): 10695–10718. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.5b05974>
- Muğlu H, Çavuş MS, Bakır T, Yakan H (2019) Synthesis, characterization, quantum chemical calculations and antioxidant activity of new bis-isatin carbohydrazone and thiocarbohydrazone derivatives. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1196: 819–827. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2019.07.002>
- Nalini R, Basavarajaiah SM, Nagesh GY, Mohammad J, Ramakrishna Reddy K (2023) Synthesis, characterization, DFT analysis, biological evaluation, and molecular docking of Schiff base derived from isatin–isoniazid and its metal(II) complexes. *Polycyclic Aromatic Compounds* 43(8): 7597–7614. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10406638.2022.2138927>
- Parakkal S, Lalnunfeli H, Sidan S, Datta R (2023) Spirocyclic isatin-derivative analogues: Solvation, structural, electronic, topological, reactivity properties, and anti-leukaemic biological evaluation. *Computational and Theoretical Chemistry* 1225: 114163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comptc.2023.114163>
- Parr RG, Pearson RG (1983) Absolute hardness: Companion parameter to absolute electronegativity. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 105: 7512–7516. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00364a005>
- Parr RG, von Szentpály L, Liu S (1999) Electrophilicity index. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 121: 1922–1924. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja983494x>
- Patil S, Alegaon SG, Gharge S, Ranade SD, Khatib NA (2024) Molecular hybridization, synthesis, in vitro α -glucosidase inhibition, in vivo antidiabetic activity and computational studies of isatin-based compounds. *Bioorganic Chemistry* 153: 107783. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2024.107783>
- Raksha C, Ansiya N, Sreekumar A, Elambalassery J, Sivan A (2025) Isatin–fluorene Schiff base as potent antidiabetic agent: Synthesis, DFT calculations, topology, in silico ADME analysis and molecular docking studies. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1322(3): 140551. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2024.140551>

- Rasgania J, Gavadia R, Nimesh S, Loveleen L, Mor S, Singh D, Jakhar K (2023) Synthesis of isatin-tagged thiadiazoles as anti-breast cancer leads: In vitro and in silico investigations. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1294(2): 136464. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2023.136464>
- Sharma PK, Balwani S, Mathur D, Malhotra S, Singh BK, Prasad AK, Len C, Van der Eycken EV, Ghosh B, Richards NG, Parmar VS (2016) Synthesis and anti-inflammatory activity evaluation of novel triazolyl-isatin hybrids. *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry* 31(6): 1520–1526. <https://doi.org/10.3109/14756366.2016.1151015>
- Singh GS, Desta ZY (2012) Isatins as privileged molecules in design and synthesis of spiro-fused cyclic frameworks. *Chemical Reviews* 112(11): 6104–6155. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr300135y>
- Yakan H, Çavuş MS, Zengin Kurt B, Muğlu H, Sönmez F, Güzel E (2021) A new series of asymmetric bis-isatin derivatives containing urea/thiourea moiety: Preparation, spectroscopic elucidation, antioxidant properties and theoretical calculations. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1239: 130495. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2021.130495>